

NORMALISATION OF IMPRECISE TEMPORAL EXPRESSIONS IN THE TEXT

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Abstract. *Information extraction systems play a crucial role in managing the vast amount of unstructured data available today. Extracting temporal information from text documents is particularly challenging due to the varied nature of temporal expressions, such as "less than 2 years" or "several weeks," which can be imprecise and difficult to normalize accurately. This can lead to errors in understanding the chronological order of events extracted from the text. While there are approaches available to represent imprecise temporal expressions, they may not always be tailored to specific scenarios and can be challenging to generalize across different contexts.*

Keywords: *imprecise temporal expressions (timex), imprecise timex normalisation, temporal information extraction, imprecise temporal representation*

The article highlights the significance of time as a fundamental element that enables us to perceive, describe, and make sense of the world around us. Time serves as a crucial factor in our cognitive and linguistic processes, allowing us to articulate changes that occur through events, processes, and actions. It facilitates the recording, sequencing, and quantification of the duration of these occurrences. Given its pervasive nature in human existence, accurately identifying temporal order is essential. Failure to do so can lead to misunderstandings and hinder comprehension. Therefore, effective management and interpretation of time-related information are vital for ensuring clear communication and understanding in various contexts

The extraction of temporal information from text is crucial for understanding language and is a key component in various language processing applications like text summarization and knowledge base population. Processing temporal expressions involves tasks such as recognizing and representing temporal information. Solving complex computational problems related to time has been essential in the advancement of information extraction systems. Sometimes, temporal expressions in text are imprecisely described, indicating an approximate amount or point in time, such as "about 3 months ago," "less than a year," "few days," and "recently." In certain text types like clinical notes, over 30% of temporal information can be imprecise, impacting search results for events associated with such temporal data. Furthermore, an inaccurate interpretation can lead to different values for the same expression. Hence, it is crucial to standardize values for imprecise temporal expressions for a given application, a process known as normalization. TimeML is a significant initiative for annotating temporal information in text, having been an ISO standard since 2010. It aims to link the process of temporal analysis with a formal representation of time, offering a model and annotation scheme for temporal data, including the TIMEX3 scheme for representing temporal expressions. However, while TimeML can describe imprecise temporal expressions in terms of language structure, it lacks mechanisms for accurately normalizing them. This can lead to ambiguity or incompleteness in the normalization of imprecise temporal data values.

Existing approaches address the issue by using fuzzy sets to represent individual temporal expressions and relationships. These approaches typically focus on specific historical events or generic time periods, relying on external data sources like internet search results or social media timestamps. However, they do not offer a generic or reusable methodology for normalizing

imprecise temporal expressions. Instead, normalization is often based on extracted time spans that are limited in their interpretation of temporal expressions, making them challenging to apply to broader domains. The process of reading and understanding a text involves inferring whether the situations presented in the text occur at specific points in time. Organizing events in chronological order is crucial for identifying temporal relations, such as before/after relationships among them. Temporal information extraction plays a key role in this process. Temporal expressions in natural language can directly refer to time points or intervals (e.g., "6 years ago"), acting as anchors for linking concepts and events extracted from the text to a timeline. This helps in accurately placing extracted elements in time. However, recognizing temporal expressions (timexes) in text is a complex task that involves various linguistic entities and sources of knowledge. The annotation of temporal expressions entails finding appropriate labels ($y_1, \dots, y_n$) for a given input string of tokens ($x_1, \dots, x_n$) so that the resulting labeling can be decoded into textual spans representing the tokens and denoting time in the input string. This process is essential for understanding the temporal context of the text and establishing temporal relationships between different events and concepts mentioned in the text.

Timex normalization is crucial in capturing temporal information accurately in natural language processing. It involves tagging a timex with attribute values that describe the expression in terms of time duration or a specific point in time. The goal of timex normalization is to obtain the absolute value of a timex regardless of the linguistic variation used in the text. After recognizing a timex, the next step is to define its temporal value by assigning a value attribute to the expression. This process is typically implemented using rule-based systems to address challenges such as the infinite number of possible labels and the various ways calendar values can be expressed in natural language. Current annotation standards focus on normalizing imprecise timex expressions based on language structure or elements. For example, an expression like "few weeks" may be normalized to indicate an "undetermined period of time" or an "undetermined number of weeks," which can make it challenging to connect such expressions to a timeline without a specific numerical value.

Conclusion

Studies have shown that deviations from the expected order of events, temporal inconsistencies, and longer temporal gaps in text can increase cognitive load, hinder comprehension, and lead to difficulties in integrating information. This is often reflected in increased brain activity, such as the N400 component. Encountering temporal discontinuities within a text can also affect the accessibility of previously presented information, potentially leading to delays in responding to comprehension questions. The impact of larger time shifts on information availability may vary depending on the study methodology and the specific dependent variables chosen. Overall, research suggests that readers actively track and integrate temporal information while reading. Longer temporal gaps between events can make understanding a story more challenging, increase reading time, and reduce accessibility compared to stories with shorter temporal gaps or continuous events. This underscores the importance of considering temporal factors in text comprehension and the role of temporal discontinuities as event boundaries.

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